

Scale Up

Developed by: TOPSIM GmbH

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Keywords

Business, Competition, Cooperation, Corporate Leadership, Digitalization, Financial Management, Innovation Management, Marketing, Operations Management, Production Management, Strategic Decision-making, Technology

Figure 1. Graphic from *Scale Up*. Rights owned by TOPSIM GmbH; used here for educational review.

Introduction

Scale Up (see Figure 1) is a strategic business simulation that places participants in the role of managing a traditional scooter manufacturer. The objective is to guide the company through digital transformation and develop a sustainable business model for the future. Participants must make strategic decisions in production, marketing, finance, and human resources.

The simulation targets students, professionals, and leaders who want to train their management and decision-making skills in a realistic environment.

As a serious game, *Scale Up* combines playful elements with real economic challenges to enable practice-oriented learning. The focus lies on strategic thinking, digital transformation, and innovation management.

The game was developed by TOPSIM, has been available since 2020, and is continuously updated. It is used in various academic and corporate settings to prepare participants for complex management tasks in a digital market environment.

Facts

Release date:	Initial release: 2020. Current version: 1.7.0 (27.09.2024)
Developer:	TOPSIM GmbH
Game type:	Digital hybrid (at least one player per team requires internet access)
Number of players:	Optimum: 9–25 (3–5 groups of 3–5 persons each) per market. Multiple markets are possible. The number of players is infinitely scalable.
Format:	Asynchronous, Hybrid
Time frame:	Approx. 10–24 hours depending on how many of the six periods are played, how the simulation is run, and whether evaluations or additional tasks are included. Time and effort also depend on the intended learning outcomes.
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	Device: Tablet, PC, or laptop (minimum 720p). Browsers: Chrome, Firefox, or Safari. Internet access required.
Material:	Participants receive an introduction, a participant manual, business news, and seminar materials. Facilitators receive a facilitator handbook. Short description: https://www.topsim.com/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/Scale_Up_Flyer.pdf Blog article: https://www.topsim.com/blog/digitalisierung-mit-scale-up-meistern/
Price:	TOPSIM simulations are not free. Licensing costs depend on the simulation, number of participants, and usage model. Costs are calculated individually; for accurate pricing, direct inquiry with TOPSIM is recommended.

Resonance & Criticism

Scale Up is used primarily in companies and universities to provide practical experience in strategic management. For example, the CBS International Business School in Mainz uses it in interdisciplinary courses where students from different programs collaborate, bringing diverse perspectives into the decision-making process (TOPSIM GmbH, 2022b).

Exact user numbers or distribution statistics are not publicly available, but participant and expert feedback is predominantly positive. At Hochschule Osnabrück, students showed great enthusiasm and applied theoretical lecture content in practice (TOPSIM GmbH, 2020). No specific awards or critical reviews of Scale Up are publicly documented.

Game Principle & Process

In Scale Up, participants act as executives of a scooter manufacturer transitioning its business model towards electric mobility. The round-based simulation consists of up to six periods, with each team making up to 40 decisions per period across finance and accounting, research and development, procurement, sales, production, and human resources.

The simulation places special emphasis on developing and scaling new business models, for instance, through choosing between traditional and digital sales and service platforms, and on balancing physical sales channels with online marketing budgets. Economic news and VUCA scenarios introduce disruptions and volatility from the beginning, teaching participants how to manage digital transformation processes under uncertainty.

The goal is sustainable growth in company value, profit, and market share. After each period, the TOPSIM Cloud generates automated reports containing financial and production metrics as well as competitive benchmarks. These provide immediate, data-driven feedback and support an iterative learning process.

Teams consist of three to five participants. Four to six teams typically compete in parallel to ensure sufficient competitive pressure. Total playtime ranges between 10 and 24 hours, usually distributed over two to three sessions of 4–8 hours each.

TOPSIM offers a full-day facilitator training (8-hour live webinar) and recommends an additional 4–6 hours of self-study using manuals and demo scenarios to familiarize instructors with the interface, analytics tools, and didactic applications.

The simulation is grounded in research-based theories of business model innovation, strategic marketing, and financial management. Scale Up realistically simulates internal interdependencies and external disruption factors. It is a clearly structured digital scenario that distinguishes itself from classic business simulations by its strong focus on digital transformation mechanisms.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Scale Up imparts practice-oriented management competencies focused on scaling strategies, data-driven decision-making, and digital transformation. Participants lead a company intending to develop a sustainable business model that adapts effectively to market changes and enables long-term growth.

The simulation supports these learning goals through realistic scenarios in which participants must analyze large volumes of information and react flexibly to market changes. This dynamic environment strengthens strategic thinking as players continuously adjust their decisions to evolving competitive conditions. Regular evaluation of financial metrics and market analyses actively guides the learning process. The simulation includes a detailed feedback and reward system that facilitates reflection on decisions.

Instructors serve in a supportive and moderating role. They introduce the scenario, guide decision-making processes, and lead reflection discussions to foster knowledge transfer. Typically, one instructor per seminar is sufficient. The simulation is suitable for universities, professional training programs, and corporate learning environments focused on strategic management and business decision-making.

In addition to business-related learning goals, the simulation also strengthens social competencies. Participants work in teams, discuss strategies, and make joint decisions. This fosters communication skills, teamwork, and negotiation abilities. By basing the simulation on strategic management and digital transformation models, Scale Up provides realistic training for entrepreneurial thinking and behaviour. The simulation-based environment allows participants to apply theoretical content directly and better understand complex economic relationships.

Effectiveness

No specific empirical studies on the effectiveness of Scale Up are currently available. However, practical reports from educational institutions indicate positive effects. For instance, it was successfully integrated into programs at Hochschule Osnabrück, where students created companies and applied strategic planning. Participants demonstrated enthusiasm and improved their self-organization skills in online learning environments (TOPSIM GmbH, 2020).

At CBS International Business School in Mainz, Scale Up is used across academic programs, allowing diverse perspectives to enrich entrepreneurial orientation (TOPSIM GmbH, 2022b).

Indicators of engageability suggest that the realistic simulation and dynamic market conditions increase player engagement. While anecdotal evidence suggests positive learning effects, further empirical research is needed for definitive conclusions.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Scale Up contains no sensitive themes such as violence, drug abuse, or discrimination. The sustainability of virtual companies is partly measured through social factors, though deeper socio-political discussions are not included. Ethical considerations of corporate responsibility can be integrated through additional tasks, even if not explicitly part of the simulation.

As a digital business simulation, Scale Up poses no physical risks. However, participants with visual or motor impairments may encounter barriers without adequate accessibility adjustments. Furthermore, the simulation presumes business knowledge, which may challenge some learners.

Reviewer(s): Hannes Hamester

Sources

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